

was less aggressive, and that Xiang-Zhou No. 5 may have specific resistance genes effective against ZC15.

The cultivars that have shown durable resistance in the field have partial resistance to the races tested in this study. ■

Analysis of rice blast (BI) pathogen virulence in Egypt

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We evaluated the virulence of *Pyricularia oryzae* in B1-affected areas of the Nile Delta (governorates of Beheira, Dakhalia, Damietta, Gharbia, and Kafr el Sheikh) 1988-89 summer seasons.

Rice leaves and panicles with typical B1 lesions were collected from farmers' fields. Single lesions were placed in petri dishes with wet filter paper and incubated at 25°C until sporulation.

A group of conidia was aseptically transferred with a pointed capillary tube to rice leaf agar. For the purpose of this study, mass cultures from single lesions were considered equivalent to single conidial isolates. (Previous studies under the same test conditions had indicated that single conidial cultures derived from single lesions are of one race.)

In 1988, 10 commercial cultivars and 8 international differentials were tested against 35 isolates. In 1989, 8 commercial cultivars and international differentials were tested against 52 isolates.

Test plants grown in 40- × 20- × 10-cm plastic boxes in 10-cm rows, 5 cm apart were inoculated with aqueous spore

P. oryzae isolates virulent to commercial rice cultivars in Egypt 1988 and 1989.

Cultivar	Virulence ^a (%)	
	1988 (n=35)	1989 (n=52)
Giza 159	100	100
Giza 171	100	100
Giza 172	100	100
Reiho	100	100
Giza 175	3 ^b	2 ^a
Giza 181	0	0
GZ1368-5-4	0	nt
GZ2175-5-6	20	53
IR28	0	0
IR50	0	nt

^a (n) = number isolates tested. nt = not tested. ^b Intermediate reaction.

suspension (about 50,000/ml). Inoculated plants were left in a moist chamber for 48 h, then transferred to the greenhouse. Disease was scored 10-15 d later.

B1 virulence on local cultivars Giza 159, Giza 171, Giza 172, and Reiho was 100% both years (see table). Virulence was zero on indica cultivars IR28, IR50, and Giza 181, and rare on Giza 175. Currently popular breeding line GZ2175-5-6 was affected by 20% of the isolates in 1988 and 53% in 1989 (see table).

This increase in virulence on GZ2175-5-6 is associated with an increase in area sown to this line, from 1,000 ha in 1988 to 10,000 ha in 1989. ■

Resistance to blast (BI) in Egyptian rice varieties

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B1 is a major production constraint in Egypt. Resistance in a series of japonica varieties released in 1954-84 was short. A few indica breeding lines (IR28, IR1626-203 [Giza 181]) released in recent years retain resistance, but they have limited commercial acceptability and narrow genetic bases.

We evaluated 500 improved cultivars, breeding lines, and germplasm of diverse origin against the prevailing B1 pathogen races ID13 and IG1 in the Nile Delta.

Entries grown in the greenhouse were inoculated with two representative isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* 15 d after sowing (DAS). Temperature was maintained at 21-32°C and relative humidity at >90% for 9-11 h. Cultivars found to be resistant 45 DAS are listed in Table 1.

Fifteen varieties were evaluated against three representative virulent isolates from the rice-growing delta. Entries planted in single rows in nursery boxes were inoculated at 15 DAS with virulent isolates originating from Dakhalia, Kafr el Sheikh, and Gharbia governorates. After 48 h in the humid chamber, they were transferred to glasshouse benches. Disease was recorded 15 d later.

All tested IRRI varieties were resistant to the local B1 pathogen races (Table 2). Some of the varieties (IR50, Ratna,

Table 1. Reaction of selected rice genotypes to 2 representative *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates of Egypt.

Cultivar	Reaction to <i>P. oryzae</i> isolates	
	ID13 ^a	IG1 ^b
IRRI		
IR20	1	1
IR22	1	1
IR24	1	2
IR28	1	1
IR36	1	1
IR50	1	1
IR52	1	1
IR60	1	1
IR62	1	1
IR64	1	1
IR66	1	1
IR2003-P18-16	1	1
IR2153-338-3	1	1
IR19743-46-1	1	1
IR25571-31-1	1	1
Thailand		
RD7	1	1
RD9	1	1
RD10	1	1
RD21	1	1
RD25	1	1
S. Korea		
Iri 370	1	1
Milyang 23	2	1
Milyang24	2	1
Milyang 80	2	1
Milyang 85	2	1
Suweon 346	1	1
Japan		
BL 1	1	1
Kanto 1	1	2
Tsuyuuake	1	3
Torida 1	1	1
India		
Bala	1	1
Basmati 370	1	1
Cauvery	1	1
CO 43	1	1
Padma	2	4
Ratna	1	1
Rasi	1	1
Tella hamsa	1	1
USA		
Mars	1	1
Lemont	1	1
Mercury	1	1
Noritai	1	1
Egypt		
Agami	3	4
Giza 175	2	1
Giza 181	1	1
Giza2175-5-6	8	2
Yabani 15 (susceptible)	7	8
Giza 159 (susceptible)	8	8
Giza 172 (susceptible)	8	8
Reiho (susceptible)	8	8

^a Isolate from Sidisalem, on Giza on 2175-5-6. ^b Isolate from RRTC research farm Sakha, on Giza 172.

Cauvery) have a history of susceptibility in the tropics. IR36, Rasi, and a few